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EMPOWER

deliverables

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Results of the validation study.

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This deliverable reports on the results of the validation study for the Empower platform, that entails games for the assessment and training of executive functions and emotion competencies of children with neurodevelopmental disorders.

Description

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Table of Content

- 1. Introduction**
- 2. General description of the games content, purpose, target population, and their context of use**
- 3. Methodology of the validation study**
- 4. Results**
- 5. Conclusions**
- 6. References**
- 7. Appendices**

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#1. Introduction

This deliverable contains a report of the main findings on the study conducted to investigate the validity of the EMPOWER platform addressing the cognitive and emotional needs of children with neurodevelopmental disabilities. It addresses the study designs, the findings, and the limitations. Validity is one of the psychometric requirements for psychological and educational measurement instruments. It indicates the trustworthiness of the deductions based on the scores, while considering the entire process through which they were obtained (Guion, 1986, apud Albu, 1998). Validity evidence will be gathered about the function of the test, whether to measure, to decide, or to predict. Construct and content validity are two types of evidence that are linked to the measurement function of a test (Albu, 1998). Criterion-referenced validity is relevant for the decision and prediction functions. Two types of validity are considered: concurrent and predictive validity.

Validity evidence demonstrates that the assessments are relevant and useful for their intended purpose, which increases the likelihood that the training programs will be supported and successfully implemented. Moreover, ethical standards in psychology demand that tests and measures used in clinical, counselling, or research settings are valid. Using invalid assessments can lead to misdiagnosis, incorrect treatment plans, or unethical decision-making that potentially may harm individuals.

Usability of the games was also addressed. According to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO 9241-11), usability means the “extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in a specified context of use.”

#2. General description of the games content, purpose, target population, and their context of use

Neurodiverse children often face a range of challenges in the learning process. Many experience deficits in executive functioning—cognitive processes essential for goal-directed behaviour, such as planning, organizing, and maintaining attention. Deficits in these executive functions can hinder children's ability to manage daily responsibilities such as organizing schoolwork, maintaining focus, or regulating emotions in stressful situations. These challenges often interfere with the development of independent learning skills and successful adaptation to academic environments (Lee et al., 2011).

The Empower platform contains serious games addressing executive functions and emotion regulation. Several games tap into executive functions: sustained attention, working memory, inhibition, cognitive flexibility, and delay of gratification. Also, to address emotion regulation, 3 complex games were designed and developed, that would assess and train several skills: emotion recognition, emotion intensity awareness, emotion understanding, and emotion regulation per se. All tasks are games embedded in a scenario. All games are designed around the theme of an organic farm. Children can select the games they want to play from the main menu. The child can set up an avatar of their choice. The games are played on a laptop. Children will respond by selecting items. The games are designed based on well-known standardized tasks. Also, a series of 3 pilot studies was conducted to obtain an adequate shape of the tasks. Thus, after obtaining an adequate form of the task, we follow with a validation study.

BRIEF TASKS OVERVIEW

The sustained attention game asks children to find a target stimulus. Children watch the screen carefully and point to the object that represents a target stimulus.

The working memory game is in a visual format. The child watches sequences made up of visual stimuli, remembers these sequences, sorts them according to a criterion, and then responds by pointing to those stimuli in the order of their appearance.

Inhibition games require the child to sort according to rules, resisting the temptation to match by color.

The cognitive flexibility game requires the pupil to be able to identify and flexibly change the sorting rule of objects (e.g. vegetables, fruits). The game involves selecting fruits, vegetables, and flowers according to certain criteria: function, shape, color, and number.

The delay of gratification asks children to wait for the collection of a jar of honey and to resist the temptation to press a button that gets them a smaller amount of honey.

The emotional regulation games involve 3 different scenarios at a farm fair. Each of the 3 games is similar to activities typically played at fairs or amusement parks (Wheel of Emotions, Cornhole and Pyramid of Eggs). Two of the games (Wheel of Emotions and Cornhole) include the part of recognizing emotions through picture associations. All 3 games include naming, intensity awareness, and understanding emotions as well as emotional regulation through regulation strategies. In each of the games, the child encounters an obstacle or situation designed to induce emotions, both positive and negative. After naming the emotion they feel, the children have to indicate the intensity of the emotion they feel, answer the question why they feel that way, and whether and by which strategies they want to change the emotion.

The tasks are designed to be used repeatedly, as the items per level are randomly introduced, giving a different experience, yet at the same level of difficulty, based on the same principles.

The tasks are synthesized in **Appendix 1**.

PURPOSE OF THE TASKS:

two-fold, to assess and train the skills enumerated above; from a validation study perspective, it is the measuring purpose, not the decision or the prediction.

TARGET POPULATION:

children with neurodevelopmental disorders (intellectual disabilities (ID), autism spectrum disorders (ASD), Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), specific learning disorder (SLD)), ages between 6- 14 years old.

CONTEXT OF USE:

digital tasks that can be administered via a laptop, with minimal surveillance from the teacher.

Its uses:

- ✚ to give an overview of the skills that need improvement;
- ✚ to collect information on executive functions and emotion regulation from several (more than one) direct digital tasks;
- ✚ to use them repeatedly for training.

#3. Methodology

RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

Given the aim of the study and the functions of the tasks included in the Empower platform, our research questions are:

- How well do the designed tasks correlate with other established measures of the same construct?
- Are the tasks predictive of relevant outcomes (academic, emotional competence)?

The research received approval from the Ethical Committee of the Babeş- Bolyai University and of ISCTE.

PARTICIPANTS:

The participants were selected considering some inclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were chosen based on the purpose of the study, which is to test the validity of the EMPOWER platform, a tool developed to test and train executive functions in neurodiverse children, hence the need of a diagnosis with an NDD, which are further widely associated with executive functions (Benallie, 2023) and emotion self-regulation deficits (Costescu et. al., 2023). Other criteria were chosen based on the basic skills needed to use the platform. The criteria are:

- ✚ Ages of 7 and 14
- ✚ Has any of the following neurodevelopmental disorder (NDD) diagnoses (DSM-5-TR, APA, 2022): Intellectual developmental disorder (intellectual developmental disorder, global

developmental delay, or intellectual developmental disorder not otherwise specified); Autism Spectrum Disorders; Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (other specified and unspecified ADHD); Specific Learning Disorder (with deficits in reading, writing, or math); Other Neurodevelopmental Disorders (other specified or unspecified NDD); A combination of two or more of the above

- ✚ Has difficulty with executive functioning and/or emotional self-regulation (observed by teachers in the classroom).
- ✚ Can understand simple and brief instructions in oral and/or written language that are displayed during games
- ✚ Has no severe visual or motor impairments that would prevent him/her from seeing the screen or manipulating the components necessary for the game (e.g., a keyboard, mouse, and/or touch screen
- ✚ Not diagnosed with epilepsy;
- ✚ No pacemakers or implanted devices such as defibrillators, cochlear implants, etc.
- ✚ With a sufficient level of comprehension;
- ✚ Familiarized with technology.

A total of 87 children with NDD participated in this study, 43 from Romania and 44 from Portugal.

Of the 87, 23 were females and 64 were males.

- ✚ Ages ranged from 7 to 14 years old as such:

Table 1. Age distribution frequency

Age	Frequency
7	1
8	3
9	5
10	7
11	11
12	20
13	23
14	17

81.6% is in the 11-14 years old range, while 18.4% is in the range 7-10.

Most of the participants had more than one diagnosis. The table below presents the number of NDD diagnoses.

Table 2. Diagnosis distribution frequency

Diagnosis	Number
Intellectual disability	43
ADHD	32
ASD	21
SLD	14
Motor disorders	6
Down syndrome	5
Communication disorder	4
Other (behavioral, developmental delay, GRIN2B, agenesis of corpus callosum, global disorder, dyslexia, dysgraphia, Leigh syndrome, fetal alcoholic syndrome, ataxic syndrome, pyramidal syndrome)	22

 6 missing data

For all of the participants parent signed an informed consent (see Appendix 2).

Study design: cross-sectional, conducted in a lab-based setting.

DATA COLLECTION:

Performance on all the games was collected in two to three sessions. Direct tasks and independent measures were collected in a different session. All sessions were conducted in a separate room, free from distractors, and the tasks were administered individually.

INSTRUMENTS:

Convergent validity measures

Childhood executive functioning inventory for parents and teachers (CHEXI) (Thorell & Nyberg, 2008) is a 24-item instrument addressing working memory, planning, inhibition, and regulation. It has an acceptable level of test-retest reliability (reported for 2-4 week interval), 0.89 for the total score, with 0.86 for inhibition and 0.75 for working memory. A reliability analysis was conducted on the current sample, and it yielded an alpha Cronbach of 0.96, which indicates an excellent reliability.

Executive Skills Checklist (ESC)(Diamond, 2016, Diamond & Ling, 2016) has for the attention scale an alpha Cronbach of 0,9 on the current sample; the cognitive flexibility subscale from ESC yielded a 0.92 alpha Cronbach on the current sample.

REMEX – Assessing executive functions in children - direct tasks (REMEX)(Costescu, David, Roşan, Cozma & Pădure, under review)

Visual attention task adapted from NEPSY (Korkman, Kirk & Kemp, 2007)

Delay of gratification task adapted from Kochanska et al. (1996)

Academic emotion regulation questionnaire (AERQ) (Burić, Soric, & Penezic, 2016)- 16 items, alpha Cronbach 0.88- acceptable

The Assessment of Children’s Emotion Skills (ACES) (Schultz, Izard, Bear, 2004) contains 3 subtests: emotion recognition of facial expression, emotion recognition of behavior (based on behavioural descriptions), and emotion knowledge based on situation vignettes. It assesses the ability to recognize emotional arousal. It contains 56 items. The reported reliability results in various studies are mixed (Vergara et al., 2022). Most of them, however, indicate values of alpha Cronbach that make the instrument acceptable for research purposes.

Criterion measures

- **Strengths and difficulties questionnaire (SDQ)** (Goodman, 1997)- 25 items, on the current sample, an alpha Cronbach of 0.72 – acceptable for research
- **Academic Performance Rating Scale** (DuPaul, Rapport & Perriello, 1991)- 19 items, alpha Cronbach of 0.91 on the current sample

Usability measure

Teacher usability questionnaire is completed by the teacher at the end of the session and the questions measure how suitable the games are for the child. It has a total of 12 items, 10 (1 to 10) of them and the last 2 items are questions with multiple choice answers which are covering suggestions for improvement and the most enjoyable part of the game for the child. (e.g. "Are the starting points easy enough for the children to get engaged in the game?"; "Is this game, the way it is designed, engaging for the child?").

Reliability: we addressed the stability of measurement with the test-retest method, by collecting data for 7 participants with NDD.

VALIDATION METHODS

Construct Validity:

Convergent Validity Proofs: Examine correlations between the test and other measures of the same or similar constructs.

Criterion-Related Validity:

Concurrent Validity: How well the test correlates with a current, established measure.

#4. Results

ATTENTION TASK

- **Descriptive Statistics:**

Each of the tasks was analyzed. We present the descriptive statistics for the task of sustained attention.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics for the Sustained attention game

Attention scores	N	min	max	mean	σ
L1-CP	82	0	18	15,76	3,72
L2- CP	74	7	18	16,51	2,15
L3-CP	73	2	18	16,41	2,87
L1-MRT	82	0.42	4.43	0.89	0.7
L2- MRT	74	0.38	1.56	0.71	0.21
L3-MRT	73	0.48	2.07	0.81	0.29

CP- number of responses to target stimuli; MRT- mean response time; L1- level 1; L2- level2; L3- level 3.

Difficulty of the task

For attention, the maximum score is 18. On level 1, 79.3% have scored between 16-18 points. On level 2, 80% scored between 18-20, while on level 3, 79.5%.

Reliability: accuracy score on level one did not correlate significantly with the initial score ($\rho(7) = -0,25$, ns.). However, the mean response time measure in level one correlated significantly with the initial mean response time score ($\rho(7) = 0,85$, $p = .01$). For level 2, the same situation was present; the accuracy measure does not seem to be stable in time. Here, the MRT measure on the small sample did not correlate. On level 3, the accuracy score correlations are close to significance ($\rho(7) = 0,86$, $p = 0,058$), while the mean response time does not.

Convergent validity was addressed by correlating the scores obtained with the Mushroom hunters game with the scores from ESC attention and the accuracy score from the direct visual attention task. Level one scores of accuracy correlated significantly with ESC attention, such as $r(51) = -.387$, $p = .005$, so did the mean response time score with ESC attention score, $r(51) = .425$, $p = .002$. Level 2 MRT score also correlated with ESC attention, $r(46) = .298$, $p = .05$. Also, the same level task correlated moderately and significantly with the accuracy score from the direct measure task: $r(70) = .596$, $p < .0001$. Mean response time score correlated with the accuracy score $r(70) = -.515$, $p < .0001$. Level 3 accuracy score and mean response time did not correlate with the direct and indirect measures. This result may be linked to the high number of responses close to or at the ceiling.

The task, as it is in the attention game for level 3, did not correlate with established measures of attention, whether direct or indirect, in our sample. Validity indices obtained for levels 1 and 2 are acceptable to good.

WORKING MEMORY TASK

The descriptive statistics for the scores on the Working memory tasks are present in the table below:

Table 4. Descriptive statistics for the Working memory game

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
L1_COR	81	,00	10,00	5,33	3,49
L1_LS	81	,00	2,00	1,64	,61
L2_COR	33	,00	15,00	11,60	3,56
L2_LS	33	,00	3,00	2,90	,52
L3_COR	20	11,00	20,00	17,00	3,11
L3_LS	20	4,00	4,00	4,00	,00

L1,L2, L3- levels; COR: recall in the correct order; LS- longest sequence

Convergent validity was addressed by correlating the correct order of recall score on level 1 (that has sequences of 2 peppers) and the longest sequence score with the direct and indirect measures of working memory. COR score correlated with the CHEXI working memory score, $r(50) = -.437$, $p < .001$, and with the direct raw score of the working memory task, $r(69) = .353$, $p < .001$. We have obtained a moderate association with the CHEXI working memory score and a weak to moderate association with the direct task raw score. For level 2, we employed Pearson correlation, COR score correlated with CHEXI working memory total score, $r(21) = -0.478$, $p = 0,028$; longest sequence correlated significantly with CHEXI working memory total score $r(21) = -0,526$, $p = 0,014$. We employed Spearman correlation for measures on level 3. None correlated with the CHEXI working memory total score (based on 10 participants' data). As far as the associations of the COR and LS scores in level 2 and 3 with the direct measure of working memory only the correct recall score on level 2 correlated significantly ($\rho(28) = 0,44$, $p = 0,018$). Validity indices for level one and two of working memory are acceptable to good. Validity indices for level 3 are nonsignificant.

INHIBITION TASK

Descriptive statistics are presented in the table below:

Table 5. Descriptive statistics for the Inhibition task

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
L1_CC	82	2,00	6,00	5,48	,98
L1_CI	82	,00	6,00	4,95	1,74
L1_Comis_err	82	,00	8,00	1,53	2,43
L2_CC	65	,00	6,00	4,95	1,36
L2_CI	65	,00	6,00	4,66	1,68
L2_Comis_err	65	,00	4,00	,75	1,06
L3_CC	47	,00	6,00	4,42	1,48
L3_CI	47	,00	6,00	3,95	1,98
L3_Comis_err	47	,00	4,00	,72	1,07

L1, L2, L3- levels; CC- correct congruent; CI- correct incongruent; Comis_err- commission errors

We correlated the score CI with the total number of errors in the Inhibition direct task, and with the Chexi inhibition score, for each of the three levels. On level 1, CI correlated with the error score, $r(70) = -.382$, $p < .001$, and with CHEXI inhibition score, $r(51) = -.290$, $p < .05$. On level 2, the CI score did not correlate with CHEXI inhibition score, but with the direct error score, yielding a moderate correlation, $r(55) = -.573$. The CI score in level 3 did not correlate with either of the two measures. We also ran analyses to see if the CC and the commission errors correlate with the direct task errors and with the CHEXI inhibition.

None of the CC and commission errors correlated with the indirect measure. However, significant correlations were observed for the CC score on each of the levels with the total error score on the inhibition direct task, as follows: Level 1: $r(70) = -.334$, $p < .005$, Level 2: $r(55) = -.549$, $p < .0001$, Level 3: $r(39) = -.541$, $p < .001$.

Validity indices derived from the correlation of the CI score with the score of CHEXI inhibition and direct task score are acceptable to very good for levels 1 and 2. Validity indices for CC scores are acceptable to very good on each of the levels, when obtained from the association with the total error score on the direct task of inhibition.

COGNITIVE FLEXIBILITY TASK

Descriptive statistics for the measures of cognitive flexibility used within the game are presented in the table below:

Table 6. Descriptive statistics for the Cognitive flexibility game

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
L1_CR	79	,00	80,00	61,05	14,52
L1_ER	79	,00	74,00	24,62	12,89
L2_CR	32	48,00	82,00	67,00	8,47
L2_ER	32	1,00	42,00	17,25	11,44
L3_CR	22	60,00	81,00	69,54	6,43
L3_ER	22	,00	21,00	9,68	6,59
L1_PE	78	,00	52,00	7,00	10,36
L1_nonPE	78	,00	74,00	18,05	13,31
L2_PE	32	,00	22,00	3,84	4,77
L2_nonPE	32	,00	35,00	13,40	9,78
L3_PE	22	,00	8,00	1,50	1,73
L3_nonPE	22	,00	19,00	8,18	5,92

CR- total number of correct responses across trial (Of 87); ER -total number of error responses across trial (of 90); L1,L2, L3- levels; PE- perseverative errors; nonPE- non-perseverative errors.

We have correlated the CR and ER scores with the flexibility score from ESC and with the direct task CF score. In level one, there was a significant, however weak correlation between ER and DT $r(69) = .334$, $p < .005$. Also, from level one, perseverative errors correlated with DT cog_flex, $r(68) = .342$, $p < .004$.

In level 2, CR correlated significantly with the direct task score, $r(27) = -.475$, $p < .05$. Between ER and DT-CF, $r(27) = .625$, $p = .0001$. Non-perseverative errors also correlated moderately with the score from the direct task, $r(27) = .647$, $p < .0001$.

There are no significant correlations of level 3 scores with the indirect and direct measures of

cognitive flexibility. Validity indices for levels one and two are good. However, level three did not yield any significant correlations.

DELAY OF GRATIFICATION

Scores on level 1, waiting time and await all correlated with the waiting time from the direct task, within the weak range, but they did not correlate with DG difficulty waiting, nor with CHEXI regulation score.

On level 2 only the association between AW1 and CHEXI regulation was significant, $r(30) = -.416$, $p < .05$. None of the scores correlated with the waiting time on the direct task. On Level 3, none of the raw scores correlated with the waiting time and CHEXI regulation score. The validity proof for this game is rather scarce. However, there partial evidence for acceptable and good validity for levels 1 and 2.

EMOTION GAMES

Wheel emotion game

An analysis of the scores' frequencies in level 1 yielded that 80,8% of children had scores of 7 and 8, which means scored at the highest point.

An analysis of the scores' frequencies in level 2 yielded that 66,1% of children had scores of 7 and 8, which means scored at the highest point.

For emotion awareness, the frequency of responses on level 1 are displayed in table 7:

Table 7. Frequency of experienced emotions:

Emotion	Freqv.	%
No data	5	5,8
ANGRY	23	26,7
HAPPY	17	19,8
INDIFFERENT	17	19,8
SAD	13	15,1
SURPRISE	11	12,8
Total	86	100

In the previous pilot, as in this study, the most frequent emotion generated by the appearance of a specific obstacle was “angry”.

Table 8. Scores for Emotion naming level 1, Wheel game

Response	Value
No response	0
ANGRY	5
HAPPY	2
INDIFFERENT	1
SAD	4
SURPRISE	3

We scored with 2 “happy”, as it is generated by playing the game itself. For “indifferent”, we gave a score of 1 as it does not resonate with the problematic situation or with playing the game. Still, it is a valid emotion.

Another way of scoring was to attribute point according to the emotion appraisal: general (1); emotional response (2); specific appraisal (3).

We correlated the emotion scores with ACES scores. However, no correlation was obtained with any of the three scores from ACES: facial expressions, emotion recognition of behaviour, or situational emotion recognition.

We correlated the number of selected adaptive emotion regulation strategies on level 1 with the score on AERQ_adaptive. However, the two did not correlate.

18,6% (16 of 86) of the participants indicated one of the 2 maladaptive strategies, whether HIDE, FIGHT, or both. These are rather infrequent. Are there problems with the maladaptive strategies we have selected, as well as with the small number compared to the adaptive strategies? Maybe

the order of introducing the questions interferes with the selection process?

For the wheel game level 2, the frequency of emotions in the group of participants is presented in the table below:

Table 9. Frequency of experienced/ named emotions Wheel game level 2:

Emotion	Freq.	%
Valid	27	31,4
INDIFFERENT	18	20,9
ENVIIOUS	15	17,4
AMAZED	13	15,1
ANXIOUS	7	8,1
PROUD	6	7

Not sure if for level 2, the situation is not ambiguous. Too many answers of “indifferent”. Also, another explanation resides in the difficulty of indicating complex emotions. There may be a need to explain these emotions before giving the task to select one of them. The anxious emotion was not the most frequent one, as opposed to our initial predictions. For this reason, no scores were attributed for naming the emotion felt.

We compared the means of the scores based on the number of correct associations. We employed t pair sample test. There is a significant difference in the mean between level 2 and level 1, $t(58)=4,16$, $p<0.001$. While on level 1, there are basic emotions, in level 2, there are complex emotions.

For emotion understanding in level 2, we attributed scores according to the depth of the appraisal: “I don’t know” (0); general (1); emotional response (2); specific appraisal (3).

We correlated the score with the scores on ACES. No relevant correlation was obtained. Also, the score on level 2 did not correlate with the score on level 1. A possible explanation resides in the fact that many have selected “indifferent” and “I don’t know”.

Cornhole game results

In the Cornhole game task of emotion matching, level 1, 41,3% had 7 and 8 correct answers. Answers are not normally distributed. The curve is asymmetric towards the right. This indicates that the matching task may still be too easy.

There is a need to increase its difficulty. The frequency of emotions felt (Cornhole game, level 1) is displayed in the table below:

Table 10. Frequency of experienced/ named emotions in Cornhole game, level 1

Emotion	Freq.	%
No data	6	7
ANGRY	16	18,6
ANXIOUS	1	1,2
HAPPY	12	14
INDIFFERENT	18	20,9
SAD	22	25,6
SURPRISE	11	12,8
Total	86	100

The most experienced emotion the children indicated is sad, followed by indifferent, angry, happy, surprise, and anxious. We have anticipated that the most felt emotion would be angry, however, the results do not support this prediction. For this reason, no scores were attributed for naming the emotion felt.

35% and 57,5% indicated 3 and 4 emotion regulation adaptive strategies. 3 participants selected the FIGHT strategy, 4 selected the Hide strategy, 2 persons chose both. We investigated whether the emotion regulation adaptive strategies correlated with the AERQ adaptive score. The results do not support an association, on the current data.

We scored the emotion understanding as such: 0- I don't know; 1- general appraisal about outcome; 2- emotional response focused appraisal; 3- specific appraisal about own emotion.

Table 11. Emotion understanding frequency distribution of scores, L1, Cornohole game

		Frequency	Valid Percent
Valid	,00	31	38,8
	1,00	10	12,5
	2,00	14	17,5
	3,00	25	31,3
	Total	80	100,0
Missing	System	6	
Total		86	

Scores of 0 make up the highest percentage, followed by scores of 3. We investigated whether the score for emotion understanding correlates with the score on AERQ adaptive and with the scores of ACES (on the three subscales). Only the first correlation was significant, though in the low range, $r(74) = 0,229, p = 0,05$.

Cornhole game level 2

47,5% gave answers 7 and 8 correct answers. The emotion matching task on level two seems to be easy. There is a need to increase its difficulty. We compared the means for correct matches in level 1 and level 2. The difference between the means is significant, $t(38) = 2,46, p = 0,018$. The mean on level 2 is lower than the mean on level 1. In level 1, the children have the task of matching basic emotions, while on level 2, the task difficulty was increased by including complex emotions.

The frequency distribution of felt emotion on a given situation is displayed in the table below

Table 12. Frequency distribution of experienced/ named emotion on a given situation, Cornhole game, level 2

Emotion	Freq.	%
No data	46	53,5
AMAZED	8	9,3
ANXIOUS	10	11,6
ENVIOUS	6	7
INDIFFERENT	15	17,4
SAD	1	1,2
Total	86	100

Only 46,5% answered. The most frequent answer is "indifferent", followed by anxious, amazed, envious, and sad. There may be a need to change the trigger situation, so the children can resonate more easily.

Emotion understanding

For the score we considered the depth of the emotion appraisal, as it was done above.

The frequency distribution per type of response is presented in the table below:

Table 13. Emotion understanding distribution of scores, L2, Cornhole game

frequency	Frequency	Valid Percent
Valid		
	,00	14
	1,00	6
	2,00	9
	3,00	11
	Total	40
		35,0
		15,0
		22,5
		27,5
		100,0
Missing	System	46
Total		86

Scores of 0 make up the highest percentage, followed by scores of 3. We investigated whether the score for emotion understanding correlates with the score on AERQ adaptive and with the scores of ACES (on the three subscales). No correlation was significant.

Emotion regulation strategies on Cornhole game, level 2:

39 answered for the adaptive strategies. 35,9% and 61,5% indicated 3 and 4 adaptive strategies. We investigated whether the emotion regulation adaptive strategies correlated with the AERQ adaptive score. The results do not support an association, based on the current data.

Egg game level 1

The most felt emotions indicated by the children are displayed in the table.

Table 14. Experienced emotion Egg game Level 1

	Frequency	Valid Percent
No answer	6	7,0
ANGRY	10	11,6
HAPPY	38	44,2
INDIFFERENT	13	15,1
SAD	10	11,6
SURPRISE	9	10,5
Total	86	100,0

We analyzed the frequency of the number of selected adaptive strategies in the level 1 Egg game.

Table 15. Frequency distribution of scores for adaptive emotion regulation strategies in Egg game, level 1

		Frequency	Valid Percent
Valid	1,00	2	2,5
	2,00	9	11,3
	3,00	24	30,0
	4,00	45	56,3
	Total	80	100,0
Missing	System	6	
Total		86	

More than half indicated four (which represents maximum). The score does not correlate with AERQ adaptive or with SDQ and ACES measures.

Egg game level 2

Similar to the other two emotion games, the children had to indicate the emotion felt in a given situation, generated through the scenario of the game.

The results are displayed in the table below:

Emotion, Egg game, L2

Table 16. Experienced emotions in Egg game, level 2

	Frequency	Valid Percent
Valid no answer	19	22,1
AMAZED	23	26,7
ANXIOUS	13	15,1
ENVIIOUS	8	9,3
INDIFFERENT	16	18,6
PROUD	6	7,0
SAD	1	1,2
Total	86	100,0

As far as the number of adaptive strategies selected in this level, the highest percentage chose 4, which represents the maximum.

Table 17. Emotion regulation adaptive strategies Egg game level 2

		Frequency	Valid Percent
Valid	1,00	2	3,0
	2,00	1	1,5
	3,00	29	43,3
	4,00	35	52,2
	Total	67	100,0
Missing	System	19	
	Total	86	

The score does not correlate with AERQ adaptive or with SDQ and ACES measures.

SUMMARY OF RESULTS ON EMOTION GAMES:

1. Emotion Identification Accuracy (Matching Scores)

Wheel Game:

Level 1: 80.8% scored 7–8 (highest scores).

Level 2: 66.1% scored 7–8.

Cornhole Game:

Level 1: 41.3% scored 7–8.

Level 2: 47.5% scored 7–8.

Egg Game:

No direct accuracy scoring reported, but emotional responses and regulation strategies were analyzed.

Conclusions

All games, especially at Level 1, appear relatively easy. Level 2 (complex emotions) shows lower mean scores and increased variability, indicating appropriate increased difficulty. There's room to make Level 1 tasks more challenging to differentiate performance.

2. Emotion Naming (Experienced Emotions)

Wheel Game:

Level 1: "Angry" most common; in line with predictions.

Level 2: High "Indifferent" response (20.9%); prediction of "Anxious" not supported.

Cornhole Game:

Level 1: "Sad" most frequent (25.6%), not "Angry" as expected.

Level 2: "Indifferent" again frequent; 53.5% gave no answer.

Egg Game:

Level 1: "Happy" was most frequent (44.2%).

Level 2: "Amazed" most common (26.7%), with 22.1% no answers.

Conclusions:

Predictions were partially confirmed. The frequent selection of "Indifferent" and high no-response rates, particularly in Level 2, may suggest ambiguity in the situations or difficulty in identifying complex emotions. Clarification or priming may help.

3. Emotion Understanding (based on the depth of appraisal)

In all games and levels, scores of 0 ("I don't know") were the most or second-most frequent. The highest appraisal level (3 = specific appraisal) was the second most frequent.

Only one significant correlation found: Cornhole Game Level 1 understanding score and AERQ-adaptive score ($r = 0.229$, $p = 0.05$).

Conclusions:

Emotion understanding appears challenging for many participants, with a substantial number unable to provide an appraisal. Minimal association with standardized emotional competence measures (ACES, AERQ) raises questions about construct alignment. Another explanation would stand in the choice of validation instruments.

4. Emotion Regulation Strategies

Across all games, most children selected the maximum number of adaptive strategies (4) in Level 1 and Level 2.

Use of maladaptive strategies (e.g., FIGHT, HIDE) was low across all tasks (under 20%).

No significant correlations were found between selected strategies and AERQ adaptive scores, or SDQ/ACES.

Conclusions:

Children appear to easily endorse adaptive strategies. It is important to investigate if this is not related to task design or question framing. Low endorsement of maladaptive strategies suggests limited validity or salience. The non-significant correlations indicate the need to investigate for any potential issues in the sensitivity of the regulation assessment.

GENERAL CONCLUSIONS

Task Difficulty

Level 1 tasks are often too easy and may need refinement for better differentiation.

Level 2 introduces appropriate complexity but may need clearer emotional context to reduce “indifferent” and “I don’t know” answers.

Emotion Measures Validity:

No strong correlations with standardized emotion assessment tools (ACES, AERQ) suggest limited concurrent validity.

Only one weak correlation (emotion understanding and AERQ in Cornhole Level 1) was significant.

Emotion Naming and Understanding:

Tasks show promise in eliciting emotional responses but need improvement in clarity and engagement, especially for complex emotions.

Emotion Regulation:

Adaptive strategies are frequently chosen, possibly due to task framing or social desirability. Maladaptive strategy detection is weak and may require reworking both content and order of presentation.

Correlations with academic measures

Attention accuracy scores from level 1 and 2 correlate weakly with APRS academic productivity. Working memory COR and LS scores do not correlate with academic success and productivity. Inhibition scores of correct incongruent and commission errors did not correlate with academic success and productivity.

Perseverative error scores from level 1 correlates with academic productivity, $r(49) = -.283, p < .05$. Cognitive flexibility L2, ER and non-perseverative errors correlate with academic productivity, $-.475$, and $-.508, p < .05$. None correlated with academic success.

In level 3 of Cognitive flexibility, there were no significant correlations with academic success and academic productivity.

Delay of gratification level 1 measures do not correlate with academic success and academic productivity. The same results are when addressing the DG level 2 and level 3.

Emotion naming measures from the Wheel and Corn games do not correlate with academic success, productivity, and impulse control from APRS.

USABILITY RESULTS

We analyzed the responses, and we report the percentages per item (for 61 answers).

Table 18. Percentages of “Yes” answers on the Teacher Usability Questionnaire

Q1. Does this game have an appropriate difficulty level for your students with neurodevelopmental disorders?	72,1%
Q2. Do your students need help understanding the task?	91,8%
Q3. Are the starting points easy enough for children to engage with the game?	83,6%
Q4. Do you find the main menu intuitive, visually informative?	91,8%
Q5. Is the estimated time to complete the task adequate?	65%
Q6. Are the instructions accessible to all your pupils?	54,1%
Q7. Is the game easy to navigate?	88,1%
Q8. Does the game need to be customisable?	80,3%
Q9. Is the game, as designed, attractive to the child?	95,1%
Q10. Can you assess its overall configuration? very poor, poor, good, excellent	79,3% gave a 2, while 20,7 gave a 3

The game is easy to navigate and attractive in design for the children, also intuitive. However, while it has adequate difficulty levels and easy starting points, it requires assistance from the teacher in order for the student to understand. Instructions as they are, are difficult for some students to understand. Only 65% found the estimated completion time adequate, indicating that the time required may need adjustment to better suit student attention spans or pacing. Its overall configuration is rated good and excellent, suggesting general approval.

#6. Conclusions

CONCLUSIONS ON CONVERGENT VALIDITY

The convergent validity of the games was evaluated by correlating performance scores across different levels of each task with both direct (performance-based) and indirect (scale-based) standardized measures. Overall, the findings indicate good to acceptable validity for most tasks at levels 1 and 2, while level 3 across domains consistently showed limited or no evidence of validity. Levels 1 and 2 of the attention task demonstrated moderate to strong correlations with both the ESC attention scores and accuracy from a direct attention task, supporting good convergent validity. In contrast, level 3 showed no significant correlations, suggesting the task at this level may not accurately assess attentional processes in its current form.

In the Working memory game, for levels 1 and 2, the correct order recall and longest sequence scores correlated significantly with both CHEXI working memory scores and the direct working memory task, indicating acceptable convergent validity. Level 3 did not produce significant correlations, possibly due to a small sample size or increased task complexity, and does not currently support validity evidence.

In Inhibition game, CI and CC scores showed moderate to strong correlations with direct task error scores and, to a lesser extent, with CHEXI inhibition scores in levels 1 and 2, confirming strong convergent validity. Although level 3 did not correlate with CHEXI, CC scores still significantly correlated with direct task errors, suggesting partial validity for this level. For Cognitive flexibility, levels 1 and 2 showed moderate to strong associations between error types and direct task performance, indicating good validity. No significant correlations were found at level 3, highlighting a lack of proof of validity at this level.

Convergent validity for delay of gratification was generally weak. Only one significant correlation was found at level 2 (AW1 with CHEXI regulation), and other associations were weak or non-significant across all levels. These results suggest that the regulation task, in its current form, lacks robust convergent validity.

None of the emotion naming scores correlated with emotional, behavioral, or prosocial measures from the SDQ. Therefore, there is no support for the convergent validity of the emotion recognition task at any level.

The table below summarizes the findings:

Table 19. Summary of validity evidence per cognitive games and levels

Domain	Level 1 Validity	Level 2 Validity	Level 3 Validity
Attention	acceptable to good	acceptable to very good	Not supported
Working Memory	acceptable to good	Good to very good	Not supported
Inhibition	acceptable	Good to very good	Partial very good
Cognitive Flexibility	acceptable	Very good	Not supported
Delay of gratification	Partial acceptable	Partial good	Not supported
Emotion Naming	Not supported	Not supported	N/A
Emotion Understanding	Partial evidence for Cornhole game	Not supported	N/A
Emotion regulation	Not supported	Not supported	

The values of the correlations range from 0,29 to 0,64, with almost 50% being under 0,45.

The findings provide solid evidence of convergent validity for the attention, working memory, inhibition, and cognitive flexibility games at levels 1 and 2. However, level 3 performance across all domains generally failed to correlate with standardized measures, indicating either increased task complexity or limitations in task design at this stage.

Tasks related to emotion recognition and regulation did not demonstrate adequate validity and may require substantial revision or reconsideration of their structure and measurement focus.

However, it is important to see the results in the context of the convergent validity measures. The selected measure addresses the different adaptive regulation strategies, while our measure offer a count of the diversity of the adaptive and maladaptive measures.

CONCLUSIONS ON CONCURRENT VALIDITY

The findings suggest that cognitive flexibility, particularly at first task levels, is the most promising predictor of academic productivity among the domains assessed. Attention showed weak associations with productivity; while working memory, inhibition, delay of gratification, and emotion recognition tasks did not demonstrate meaningful correlations with academic outcomes. These results underscore the need to further refine or differentiate game-based measures when aiming to predict educational performance or classroom behaviors. These results can also be explained in relation to the type of criterion measure.

CONCLUSIONS ON USABILITY

The games are well received. Their general appearance is intuitive, easy to navigate. However, there are some improvements recommended, as such task duration, instructions to be more accessible, provision of more autonomy in performing the tasks, and customization.

A limitation of this study is a lower representation of children aged 7–10 compared to those aged 8–14, although the target population was defined as children between 7 and 14 years old. This discrepancy may be explained by the fact that participants were recruited from special education schools, where those meeting our inclusion criteria were primarily in the older age range.

In interpreting the limited validity evidence observed in certain domains, particularly at Level 3 of the Empower platform, it is important to consider the potential cumulative effect of gameplay. By the time children reach Level 3, they have already engaged with Levels 1 and 2, which may influence their performance due to learning effects or increased task familiarity. This layered exposure can mask the distinct evaluative capacity of Level 3, thereby complicating the interpretation of its psychometric validity. Additionally, in the emotion-related games, we observed a ceiling effect, where many participants achieved near-maximum scores. This suggests that the tasks may not have

been sufficiently sensitive to detect individual differences in emotion recognition or regulation among the sampled population.

Despite these limitations, the ethical implications of using a partially validated platform were carefully considered. Throughout the study, measures were implemented to ensure participant well-being, adaptive difficulty levels, and the presence of trained professionals during sessions. Data interpretation was conducted with caution, and preliminary findings were framed as exploratory rather than conclusive.

The Empower platform is positioned as a developmental tool, and its ongoing refinement is guided by both empirical findings and ethical standards of responsible use. This includes transparent communication with stakeholders about the platform's current capabilities and limitations, ensuring that its use supports, rather than substitutes, comprehensive clinical assessment.

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APPENDIX 1. OVERVIEW OF THE TASKS FROM THE EMPOWER PLATFORM

Construct Name of the game	Description of the game	Standardized tasks	Measures	Brief description of the levels
Working memory (Worm)	A type of concurrent span (complex) task in which in between the items to remember, the peppers that ripen (turn from green to yellow) in a garden with 3 rows and 3 columns, the child has to sort into two categories (peppers with worm and peppers without worm). After the sequence ends, the child responds by indicating the peppers in order.	Computerized Corsi Blocks	Correct Pepper Sort Incorrect Pepper sort Correct Order Recall Wrong order Correct recall Longest Sequence Mean RT RT Error RT Correct Total time required Total number of trials	Level 1 – there are two peppers turning from green to yellow Level 2 – there are three peppers turning from green to yellow Level 3 – there are four peppers turning from green to yellow
Sustained attention (Mushroom Hunters)	A Comprehensive Continuous Task designed to improve the function of Sustained Attention by training the cognitive system to activate and maintain attention at an optimal level for prolonged periods of time while simultaneously inhibiting the response system. The task is based on a continuous performance test (CPT). The task involves a long series of stimuli presented (mostly) sequentially with the participant instructed to respond as fast as possible only when a pre-specified target (e.g., brown mushroom) is presented, while withholding responses to other stimuli (e.g., flowers, small branches, butterflies (targets) appearing on the screen). Action takes place in the forest – on a pathway.	The Computerized Continuous Performance Task (CCPT; based on Rosvold, Mirsky, Sarason, Bransome, & Beck, 1956).	Total Correct Answers Correct Present Correct Absent Total Incorrect Answers Error Present Error Absent Mean RT Correct Present Mean RT Error Absent RT Error RT Correct Total time required	Level 1 - Single target (central), 30%, 60 trials, with simple distractors Level 2 - Single target (close, far, central), 30%, 60 trials with static distractors (flowers, small branches, butterflies) Level 3 – Single target (close, far, central), 30%, 60

				trials with other 3 different types of mushrooms as distractors
Inhibition (ReStroop)	<p>A stroop task in which The fundamental idea is creating agreement (via congruent stimuli [C]) or conflict (via incongruent stimuli [IC]) between values of the target feature (type of trash that goes in the recycle bin) and the distractor feature (recycle bin colour) when responding to the target feature (Algom et al, 2022).</p> <p>The child has to clean up the garden and recycle the trash that he/she picks up from the ground. The child sees the respective recycle bins for each of the trash (including a bin for plastic, glass and cardboard) each in a different colour (blue, yellow, and green). They must decide if they have the appropriate trash for the correct bin. All of the recycling bins appear with the respective image of trash to put inside. They answer by touching either the check mark if the bin that opens is correct (same type of trash) or the x mark if the bin that opens is incorrect (different type of trash). Children must identify the correct type trash while inhibiting the colours of the bins and the trash.</p>	The stroop task	<p>Mean RT</p> <p>Mean RT Congruent</p> <p>Mean RT Incongruent</p> <p>Total Correct Answers</p> <p>Total Incorrect Answers</p> <p>Correct Congruent</p> <p>Correct Incongruent</p> <p>Congruent Errors</p> <p>Incongruent Errors</p> <p>Percent Trials No Answers</p> <p>RT Error</p> <p>RT Correct</p> <p>Commision errors</p> <p>Total time required</p> <p>Omission Errors</p>	<p>Level 1 – picking up the trash in the garden than recycle the trash according to the type of trash and not the color of the bin</p> <p>Level 2 – timer is added for the decision making</p> <p>Level 3 – shorter limit of time added for the decision making</p>
Cognitive flexibility (ReFlex)	<p>Successful performance in this game requires the participant to first determine the correct sorting principle on the basis of verbal and visual feedback, and then to maintain this sorting principle until a new sorting rule and set of key images is provided.</p> <p>The participants are shown crates with differing</p>	The WCST (Heaton et al. 1993)	<p>Total Trials</p> <p>Total Correct Responses</p> <p>Total number of errors</p> <p>Total Category Correct Sort</p> <p>Non-perseverative errors</p>	<p>Level 1 – 2 crates (any combination of 2: number, colour and FRUIT)</p> <p>List of shape items: grape, orange, banana, pineapple, pear</p>

	<p>shape/item, number and colour and are asked to sort different items (fruits, vegetables, flowers) that are on top of a table along an unspecified dimension (e.g., shape). Participants are not told the sorting rule but are provided with in game feedback as to whether a given match is correct or incorrect. If there was an incorrect match than the player will receive a hint in the left bottom corner with what dimension or criteria they tried before.</p> <p>There is no time limit for the completion of this game nor the presentation of stimuli (items).</p> <p>Sorting rules Shape (item): Fruit / Vegetables / Flowers Colours: Yellow, Black, Purple, Green, Orange Number: 1-5</p>		<p>Failure Maintain Set Num Trials For First Category Mean RT Correct Mean RT Incorrect RT Error RT Correct Total time required</p>	<p>Level 2 – 3 crates (any combination of 3: number, colour and VEGETABLES) List of shape items: mushroom, onion, courgette, pepper, eggplant Level 3 - 4 crates (any combination of 4: number, colour and FLOWERS) List of shape items: Cactus, roses, tulips, daisies, potos</p>
<p>Delay of gratification (BeeHold)</p>	<p>The purpose of this games is to see and eventually train the extent to which one can resist the temptation of an immediate reward and wait for a larger reward later.</p> <p>Successful performance in this game requires the participant to wait for the beekeeper in order to press the button/honey pot, so as to receive the greater reward, as opposed to clicking immediately on the button/honey pot in order to get the instant reward.</p> <p>The reward consists of different quantities of honey, depending on the level and the quantity</p>	<p>The marshmallow experiment</p>	<p>Wait Time Trial 1 Wait Time Trial 2 Wait Time Trial 3 Able to wait Trial 1 Able to wait Trial 2 Able to wait Trial 3</p>	<p>Level 1 – 3 trials of 1 minute each (1 minute until the beekeeper appears) Level 2 – 3 trials of 3 minutes each (3 minutes until the beekeeper appears) Level 3 – 3 trials of 4 minutes each (4 minutes until</p>

	of the honey doubles if the child waits for the beekeeper. Also, the honey collected can be used to play a mini game at the end of each level. The time to play depends on the quantity of honey collected.			the beekeeper appears)
Emotion naming Emotion intensity Emotion understanding Emotion regulation (Emotifest)	<p>The Emotifest takes place in a Farm Fair scenario and includes three primary games: the Wheel Game, the Cornhole Game, and the Egg Pyramid Game. Each game was designed to address specific emotional competencies, including recognition, intensity, understanding and regulation.</p> <p>The Wheel Game: The child spins a large wheel, with each section representing a different emotional expression. The task is to match the emotion on the wheel with corresponding facial expressions on cards shown to the child. This game directly addresses emotion recognition and is used to assess and train the child's ability to identify emotions based on facial expressions.</p> <p>The Cornhole Game: In this game, the child throws bean bags into raised boards, each featuring a different facial expression. The task requires the child to match the emotion on the bean bag with the correct board. This game serves as well to assess and train emotion recognition.</p> <p>The Egg Pyramid Game: In this game, the child builds an egg pyramid while competing against another player.</p> <p>Each game involves children experiencing a frustrating situation or obstacles, such as an almost impossible task of building a tower of</p>	<p>The Test of Emotion Comprehension (TEC) (Pons, Harris, & Rosnay, 2004), which measures a variety of emotional competencies. The TEC evaluates emotion recognition from facial expressions, understanding external causes of emotions, the role of desires and beliefs in emotions, the ability to regulate emotions, and the ability to</p>	<p>Wheel_naming_correct match Wheel_emotion wheel_intensity_number wheel_understanding_option wheel_regulation_options descript wheel_regulation_option adaptative wheel_regulation_option maladaptative Cornhole_naming_correct match Cornhole_naming_correct throw Cornhole_emotion Cornhole_intensity_number Cornhole_understanding_option Cornhole_regulation_options descript Cornhole_regulation_option adaptative Cornhole_regulation_option maladaptative</p>	<p>Level 1 – is featuring basic emotions: happy, sad, angry, surprised Level 2 – is featuring complex emotions: proud, amazed, envious, anxious</p>

	<p>blocks (Rohlf & Krahne, 2015), designed to elicit frustration. In the wheel game after three spins, another child (social agent) steps in front of the child and starts playing (saying "It's my turn"), and the player has to wait for 1 minute while watching the other child playing. In the cornhole game, the 4th time the child wants to "throw" a bean bag, there is a problem with the game, and the holes on the boards are covered with dirt, and the player has to wait for 1 minute while watching another character clean the boards. In the egg pyramid game, there are two different situations depending on the level. For the first level, the player is the second one to finish the pyramid, and for the second level, the eggs are cracking and chicks start coming out of them. After encountering an obstacle, the children are asked to reflect on how they feel and choose an emotional response (e.g., happy, sad, angry). Then, they rate the intensity of their emotion using a potion bottle on a three-level scale – just a little on the bottom, halfway up, or all the way up. While increasing the quantity of the potion in the bottle, the face of the avatar changes from neutral to a more intense expression of the emotion chosen. To see if the children are understanding their own emotions, they are asked why they are feeling that way, and four bubbles with options will appear. Based on their selection, feedback is provided, helping them accept the emotional response they experienced. Children are also given the option to select emotion regulation strategies from an inventory of emotion regulation strategies that we selected</p>	<p>conceal emotions, among other elements. The Emotions Thermometer (Burg, 2005) to assess emotional intensity The Tower Construction Task (Rohlf & Krahne, 2015) to assess emotion regulation.</p>	<p>Egg_emotion Egg_intensity_number Egg_understanding_option Egg_regulation_options_descript Egg_regulation_option_adaptative Egg_regulation_option_maladaptative</p>	
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	<p>based on Buric's academic emotion regulation questionnaire (2016). They can choose up to four regulation strategies, and then they can play a mini game, which differs depending on the game the child plays at the time. Furthermore, the child will be able to play again the initial game.</p>			

APPENDIX 2 FOR THE INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Parent/legal guardian informed consent form

The EMPOWER project (Design and evaluation of technological support tools to empower stakeholders in digital education) is funded by Horizon Research and Innovation Actions of the European Commission, project number 101060918.

The project aims to develop and implement a unique, inclusive and personalized educational platform for training executive functions and emotional competence in children with neurodevelopmental disorders, which will provide teachers with resources to support these children in emotional regulation and management of behavioral problems. At this stage, the project aims to investigate the effectiveness of the platform in training executive functions and emotional competence through a randomized controlled trial.

Your child is invited to participate in the study as one of 42 participants in Romania. The teacher will carry out the tests. Participants are children with neurodevelopmental disorders (NDD), aged 8-14, 42 from Romania and 42 from Portugal. Criteria of inclusion are: a. to have a neurodevelopmental diagnosis, such as Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, Autism Spectrum Disorder, Conduct disorders, Language disorders, Specific learning disorder, Intellectual disability, generic syndromes; b. to have deficits in social and/or emotional skills; c. to have adequate language comprehension skills in order to understand task instructions; d. to be familiarized with the use of a tablet. Informed consent will be requested. Also, an adapted assent (Appendix 2) form for the child will be used. Children are recruited via their teacher and School District based on clear criteria for inclusion. Given the use of eye-tracking, it will not be used for children who have epilepsy or those who have pacemakers or implanted devices such as defibrillators, cochlear implants, etc.

The activities of the project in _____ are coordinated by _____.

The project is carried out in collaboration with the following partners:

...

There is an agreement on joint responsibility for data processing between all partners in the list.

All of the above stated institutions are data controllers. The lawfulness of processing data in the project is based on that the processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest, Art. 6, 1 e) and Art. 9, 2 j). in accordance with the EU GDPR statutory law. The data will be uploaded on a secured research data server and share with the partners in the project. Partners outside Romania will only access pseudonymized personal data. A number of security measures are implemented to prevent unauthorized access to personal data.

Data management in the project is regulated through a joint data controller agreement about joint processing responsibility. Data is stored at the Edge/Donders Research Data Management system in the Netherlands. This is a certified data repository for technical and scientific research data. The data will be safely kept until 31.08.2030 and be anonymised or deleted.

Project stages:

a. Data collection for initial assessment and validation of the platform through the platform tasks described below. Completion by the child of the 8 games proposed on the tablet: sustained attention, working memory, inhibition, delay of gratification, cognitive flexibility and 3 games aimed at understanding, recognizing facial expressions, understanding emotions and using emotional regulation strategies.

The sustained attention game asks children to find a target stimulus. Children watch the screen carefully and point to the object that represents a target stimulus.

The working memory game is in visual format. The child watches sequences made up of visual stimuli, remembers these sequences, sorts them, and then responds by pointing to the stimuli in the order in which they appear.

The inhibition game requires the child to sort according to rules, resisting the temptation to match by color.

The cognitive flexibility game involves selecting fruits, vegetables and flowers according to certain criteria: function, shape, color and number.

The delay of gratification game asks children to wait to collect a jar of honey and resist the

temptation to press a button that brings them a smaller amount of honey.

Emotion understanding and emotion regulation games aim to recognize, name, understand and regulate emotions by associating pictures of faces with emotions, naming emotions experienced as a result of situations designed to elicit both positive and negative emotions, indicating the intensity of the emotions experienced and understanding why they occurred, and choosing strategies for emotional regulation.

An eye-tracking device and a fitness bracelet will be used with the digital game. Both devices are non-invasive. The bracelet will be positioned on the hand. The eye-tracking device is attached to the device being played on. This device is a Tobii Pro Nano. It will not be used for children who have epilepsy or those who have pacemakers or implanted devices such as defibrillators, cochlear implants, etc. This is also true for those who will be using the device. It should be noted that the Tobii device complies with European standards for LED lighting and is IEC/EN 62471 certified. These devices will collect behavioral and physiological data (via fitness bracelets, pulse and heart rate; eye movements via eye tracking) during play. The collection of this data is done while students are playing the games in the platform.

This stage takes about 1 h.

b. Testing children with executive functioning and emotional regulation tasks.

The tests used are the following:

REMEX – Evaluare a funcțiilor executive la copil – sarcini directe (REMEX) (Costescu, David, Roșan, Cozma & Pădure, în curs de evaluare)

Visual attention task adapted from NEPSY (Korkman, Kirk & Kemp, 2007)

Delay of gratification task adapted from Kochanska et al. (1996)

Academic Emotion Regulation Questionnaire -AERQ (Buric et al., 2016)

This test lasts about 1 hour.

Questionnaires or scales will also be used where the parent or teacher can provide information about executive functioning and emotional regulation.

These are:

Childhood executive functioning inventory for parents and teachers (CHEXI) (Thorell & Nyberg, 2008)

Executive Skills Checklist (ESC) (Diamond, 2016, Diamond, & Ling, 2016)

Strengths and difficulties questionnaire (SDQ) (Goodman, 1997)

Academic Performance Rating Scale (APRS) (DuPaul, Rapport & Perriello, 1991)

c. randomization (random distribution in groups) in the 2 groups: a group in which the students will benefit from the classroom activities and an experimental group in which the students will participate in a number of 20 sessions of 30 min each, in which they will play the educational games of the platform, in a random order.

d. participation in one of the 2 study groups;

e. final evaluation, both in terms of performance on the platform games and through the tests of executive functioning and emotional competence mentioned in point b.

The implementation team will be led by:...

Confidentiality:

All data collected will be kept confidential and child identifying information will not be mentioned in the studies. Access to information will be limited to members of the research team only. Data will be anonymized. Data will be used for research purposes only. The data collected will be kept secure until October 2030, when personal data will be deleted. The anonymized data will be shared in open databases without identification being possible.

Personal data will be collected directly through the participants and their parents, and sensitive data relating to the child's NDD diagnosis will also be recorded. Each participant will have their data encoded through an ID code, to assure pseudonymization. Consent of data subjects is in accordance with the EU GDPR statutory law.

Withdrawal:

Participation in the study is completely voluntary and your child's personal data will only be processed with your consent.

Participation or non- participation will not have any influence on the quality of teaching or relationship with the teachers. Expressing interest in the study does not require you to participate. Even if you initially decide to participate and then change your mind, you can

withdraw at any time without any negative consequences for you and without stating a reason. The research team also has the right to stop your child's participation in the study. This decision may be made if your child shows an unwillingness to interact with the tablet or other devices mentioned above, or if your child shows an increased level of distress.

If you are interested and would like to enroll your child in this project, please fill out the enrollment form below, while keeping in mind that as long as your child can be identified in the data collected, you have the right to:

- have access to the personal data that is being processed about your child;
- to request erasure of your child's personal data;
- to request the correction/rectification of incorrect personal data relating to your child;
- receive a copy of your child's personal data (data portability); and
- the right to lodge a complaint to a supervisory authority.

Application form:

Full name/ surname of parent/legal guardian:

Child's first and last name:

E-mail Address:

Telephone number:

Child's age:

Diagnosis:

Date of birth (day month year)

I consent to my child's participation in this study.

Date Signature

